

Teachers' Experiences in Multi-Grade Instruction: A Meta-Synthesis

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Article Info	Abstract
Article History	<p><i>This study presented a meta-synthesis of teachers' experiences in teaching multi-grade classes across countries. It utilized 18 studies out of the initial 89 studies from the PRISMA using Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (CASP) checklist. Constant comparison and the use of thematic analysis resulted to eleven (11) themes and two emerging meta-themes were generated. Results indicated that multi-grade teachers have different experiences and coping mechanism in teaching. Teachers experienced success in multi-grade teaching when they cultivate whole-hearted commitment, sense of accomplishment and recognize the value and usefulness of multi-grade teaching. Challenges experienced by the teachers included being left behind, inadequacy in multi-grade teaching, difficulty in classroom and time management, failure to address learners' diversity and burnout syndrome in teaching. Their personal and professional qualities of being resourceful, innovative and resilient made them stand despite of the challenges they encountered. Multi-grade teaching is a continuous training from teacher preparation to professional development. Academic institutions should provide strong immersive internship partnership with schools and community. It is recommended that induction, mentoring and certification programs on multi-grade instruction should respond to the needs of multi-grade teachers in the teaching learning process of diverse groups of students.</i></p>
Received: May 11, 2021	
Accepted: October 13, 2021	
Keywords :	
Meta-synthesis, Multi-grade teaching, Teachers' experiences, Multi-grade instruction, Systematic Review	
DOI:	
10.5281/zenodo.5567812	

Introduction

Multi-grade class instruction is a type of education that addresses the needs of developing and less developed countries by eliminating illiteracy in the face of teacher shortages and enabling in the achievement of "Education for All" (EFA) in order to provide access to education for all people irrespective of background, skin color and age (Mulryan-Kyne, 2007; Little, 2006).

Teachers found obstacles and opportunities in molding their teaching experiences in rural communities despite the fact that multi-grade education has progressed a long way. Research studies reported that in teaching multi-grade classes problems of insufficient time, lack of teaching experiences, poor students' performance, diversity of students' age, grade level, and deficiency of learning materials and resources and the like were identified (Bashiri et al, 2015; Mortazavizadeh 2014; Aghazadeh & Fazli, 2013; Ngubane, 2011; Asadi, 2011).

Multi-grade teachers are among the highly driven workforce that puts the chance to impact child development and serve marginalized children in remote communities. Likewise, they group students, teach a variety of subjects with limited professional development opportunities, exercise leadership and autonomy in isolated and unsupported multi-grade schools (OECD, 2019, Mulryan-Kyne, 2007). They struggle balancing their tasks as classroom teachers of diverse students and community leaders of deprived communities (Rafiq & Sultana, 2020; Mortazavizadeh et al, 2017).

Muusa-Maria & Maija, (2016) narrated that while teachers are working in a unique environment, it is also evident that they have positive experiences. They relished in their teaching careers due to the rewarding aspects of the job in recognizing the value of multi-grade instruction especially for pupils' cognitive and social development. Brown (2010) emphasized the importance of multigrade teaching in supporting long-term human development in underserved communities. Hyry-Beihammer and Hascher (2015) suggested that multigrade teaching is a promising teaching arrangement when the heterogeneity of students is taken into account and cultivated. Teachers have a sense of accomplishment when they see their students succeed (Grimes, 2019).

The portrait of the experiences of multi-grade teachers labels them as educationally challenging, rich in motivations and responsibilities, yet burden with heavy teaching and administrative duties on issues surrounding their work in rural schools.

Several studies were conducted on teachers' experiences in multi-grade teaching and learning from less developed or developing countries. Many of which were focused on the insights of the teacher's pedagogies in multi-grade classrooms and the needs of practicing multi-grade teachers. However, none has conducted a study on meta-synthesis of teachers' experiences in multi-grade instruction. Hence, this study aims to meta-synthesize research studies on multi-grade teaching experiences across countries.

Research Questions

This study aims to meta-synthesize research articles regarding multi-grade teaching. Specifically, it aims to answer the following questions:

1. What are the teachers' good experiences in multi-grade teaching?
2. What are the teachers' challenges in multi-grade teaching?
3. How do teachers overcome/resolve the challenges?

Methodology

In the study, meta-synthesis is employed to develop an evidence-based explanation of the occurrence (Finfgeld-Connet, 2008) on multi-grade teaching experiences across countries.

Search Strategy

A scholarly electronic repository was used to identify manuscripts published in English language journals related to Teacher's Experience in Multi-Grade Instruction through Google Scholar database via Publish or Perish software. All of the studies relevant to the teachers' experience in multi-grade instruction published from 2010 to 2020 were downloaded and analyzed. Keywords used are multi-grade teaching, teachers' experience, phenomenological study, case study. To narrow the search, another keyword was entered in the title section using the key term — multi-grade. These terms were specifically chosen to extract data from Google Scholar in order to accumulate variables required for the meta-synthesis.

Selection/Inclusion Criteria

The studies in this review were chosen based on the following criteria: articles must be peer reviewed, reported in English, involve multi-grade teaching, focused on teachers' experience on multi-grade instruction, 2010-2021 studies, and must qualify using the Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (CASP) checklist.

Search Result

Figure 1 shows the search result in identifying the studies to be included in the meta-synthesis.

Figure 1. The three-stage flow chart of qualitative research paper selection

Three (3) stages of the research paper

selection using the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) Flow Diagram by Page, et al (2021) was utilized. Identification, Screening, and Included are the three phases. Identification is the initial stage where eighty-nine (89) studies were identified through Google Scholar database using Publish or Perish software. Fifteen (15) studies were excluded because the studies were not written in English, thus resulted to Seventy-four (74) studies.

There were two (2) sub-stages used in the screening stage. On the first sub-stage, fifty (50) studies were omitted because of the unavailability of resources, resulting to twenty-four (24) studies remaining. Using the CASP Checklist for intensive screening, six (6) studies were excluded in the second sub-stage which resulted to the eighteen (18) included studies in the last stage.

Data Analysis

The selected data had undergone constant comparison and were analyzed using thematic analysis as defined by Caulfield (2020). The research protocol of Clarke and Braun (2017) was modified using the six-step guideline to thematic analysis. These were as follows: 1) familiarizing of the research articles or studies were noting down of initial codes was done; 2) producing initial codes by compiling data pertinent to each code; 3.) searching for themes by gathering relevant data for each theme; 4.) involving reviewing themes through making a thematic map; 5.) defining and naming themes that clearly specify the emerging themes; and 6.) producing the report through discussion of analysis and implications of the study.

Results and Discussion

The final collection of 18 studies included twelve (12) research journal articles, five (5) thesis, and one (1) dissertation. Authors were affiliated with institutes located in Asia (5 publications), Africa (11 publications), and Europe (2 publications). The eighteen (18) publications utilized in the study resulted in eleven (11) themes and emerging two (2) meta-themes. Table 1 below provides the overview and characterization of the final collection of 18 studies included in the meta-synthesis.

Table 1 below provides the overview and characterization of the final collection of 18 studies included in the meta-synthesis.

No.	Title	Year	Setting	Code
1.	Challenges Experienced by Teachers of Multi-grade Classes in Primary Schools at Nzhelele East Circuit	2016	Africa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Burnout syndrome in teaching • Inadequacy in Multi-grade Teaching • Teachers' Resourcefulness • Teachers' innovativeness
2.	Handling multi-grade teaching: It's educational implication towards teachers' competence	2020	Philippines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Burnout syndrome in teaching • Inadequacy in Multi-grade Teaching
3.	Exploring Instructional Leadership Practices within the context of Multi-grade Teaching: Experiences of Principals and Teachers	2016	Africa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inadequacy in Multi-grade Teaching • Being left behind • Burnout syndrome in teaching • Failing to address Learners' diversity • Teachers' Resiliency • Teachers' Resourcefulness • Teachers' innovativeness
4.	Multi-grade Teaching: A Daunting Challenge for Rural Teachers	2014	Africa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inadequacy in Multi-grade Teaching • Failing to address Learners' diversity • Teachers' Resourcefulness
5.	One teacher's experiences of teaching reading in an urban multi-grade foundation phase class	2016	Africa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Failing to address Learners' diversity • Inadequacy in Multi-grade Teaching • Difficulty in handling classroom and time management • Teachers' Resourcefulness • Teachers' innovativeness
6.	Multi-grade Teaching and Quality of Education in South African Rural Schools: Educators' Experiences	2012	South Africa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inadequacy in Multi-grade Teaching • Burnout syndrome in teaching • Being left behind • Difficulty in handling classroom and

				time management
7.	Teaching reading in a multi-grade class: Teachers' adaptive skills and teacher agency in teaching across grade R and grade 1	2016	Africa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inadequacy in Multi-grade Teaching • Failing to address Learners' diversity • Teachers' Resourcefulness • Teachers' innovativeness
8.	Discovering Multigrade Classes and Their Challenges and Benefits through Teachers' Experience	2016	Finland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Embracing Multi-grade Teaching • Self- fulfilment in multi-grade teaching • Wholehearted commitment • Difficulty in handling classroom and time management • Burnout syndrome in teaching • Inadequacy in Multigrade Teaching • Failing to address Learners' diversity • Teachers' Resiliency • Teachers' Resourcefulness • Teachers' innovativeness
9.	Teaching and Learning in Multi-graded Classrooms: Is it Sustainable?	2020	Turkey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulty in handling classroom and time management • Inadequacy in Multi-grade Teaching
10.	Quality Basic Education for All: Challenges in Multi-Grade Teaching in Rural Schools	2014	Africa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Being left behind • Inadequacy in Multigrade Teaching • Difficulty in handling classroom and time management • Teachers' Resiliency • Teachers' Resourcefulness
11.	Teachers' Accounts of the Usefulness of Multigrade Teaching in Promoting Sustainable Human-Development Related Outcomes in Rural South Africa	2010	South Africa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Embracing Multi-grade Teaching • Inadequacy in Multi-grade Teaching • Difficulty in handling classroom and time management • Burnout syndrome in teaching • Failing to address Learners' diversity • Teachers' Resourcefulness • Teachers' innovativeness
12.	Teacher's perceptions about multi-age classes applications: A qualitative research	2014	Africa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Failing to address Learners' diversity • Difficulty in handling classroom and time management • Inadequacy in Multi-grade Teaching • Burnout syndrome in teaching • Being left behind • Teachers' Resourcefulness • Teachers' innovativeness • Teachers' Resiliency
13.	Gender Comparison on Teaching Practices of One Teacher Schools	2020	Pakistan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulty in handling classroom and time management • Inadequacy in Multi-grade Teaching • Burnout syndrome in teaching • Teachers' Resiliency • Teachers' Resourcefulness • Teachers' innovativeness
14.	Teachers Teaching Multi-Grade Classes in a Rural Setting	2011	Africa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Being left behind • Inadequacy in Multi-grade Teaching • Difficulty in handling classroom and time management • Failing to address Learners' diversity • Burnout syndrome in teaching

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teachers' Resiliency • Teachers' Resourcefulness • Teachers' innovativeness
15.	Multi-grade teaching practices in Austrian and Finnish primary schools	2015	Austria & Finland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wholehearted commitment • Embracing Multi-grade Teaching • Self-fulfilment in Multi-grade teaching
16.	Learning and Sharing: Understanding Experiences in Teaching Indigenous Learners of Mindoro	2020	Philippines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wholehearted commitment • Inadequacy in Multi-grade Teaching
17.	An Investigation of Teachers' Perceptions of the Benefits of Multi-Grade Settings in Irish Primary Schools	2019	Ireland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-fulfillment in MG teaching
18.	Educators' Perception and Experiences of Multi-grade Primary Schools	2015	Africa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inadequacy in Multi-grade Teaching • Difficulty in handling classroom and time management • Teachers' Resourcefulness

Transforming learning and achieving equity in global education remain a challenge across countries specifically on developing and less developed countries. Multi-grade teachers from Europe and Australia faced positive experiences in multi-grade instruction as a teaching modality. However, teachers from Asia and Africa encountered more obstacles in the delivery of multi-grade teaching for increasing access to inclusive, equitable, and quality education.

The eighteen (18) publications used in the study resulted to eleven (11) themes and emerging two (2) meta-themes from the experiences of the one hundred seventy-nine (179) teachers. The first three (1-3) themes were categorized as positive experiences or successes of multi-grade teachers, fourth to eighth (4-8) themes were categorized as challenges and the remaining themes (9-11) were categorized as addressing the challenges of multi-grade teaching.

Success of Multi-grade Teaching

This category describes the multi-grade teachers' positive and encouraging experiences in the delivery of multi-grade instruction that surfaced in the thematic analysis. Five (5) out of the eighteen (18) studies from Australia and European countries cited that teacher expressed rewarding exposure as they relish in their teaching journey in multi-grade instruction.

Theme 1: Having whole-hearted commitment in teaching.

The teachers have realized that teaching multi-grade developed their passion, dedication and commitment for teaching. Seeing the economic status of their learners, the isolation of the community, the curiosity and interest of the learners, made the teachers grasped how much their students needed their services. Passionate teachers recognized and endeavor to fulfill their responsibilities to the diverse students. The development of the students' achievement is always the teacher's priority (Muusa-Maria & Maija, 2016). Teachers with a strong feeling of duty, ownership, and success were likewise committed to the learning process (Afandi et al, 2021). Indeed, teaching is a never-ending commitment (Robinos et al., 2020).

Theme 2: Having a sense of accomplishment in teaching

The teachers expressed satisfaction and fulfillment with their job when they saw progress among their students. Teachers showed enthusiasm when students acquired the expected competencies (Muusa-Maria & Maija 2016). It matters most to them when both cognitive and social competencies of the learners improved given the limited resources, they have in multi-grade schools (Kivunja and Sims, 2018). They were proud to be teachers because they responded to the current condition and circumstances in rural schools and employed various motivational approaches for teaching to impact academic achievement of learners (Shah, 2009; Brown, 2010; Hyry-Beihammera&Hascher, 2015).

Theme 3: Recognizing the value and usefulness of the MG teaching

Teachers' experiences made them realize the importance of multi-grade teaching. It is beneficial for pupils' cognitive and social development (Muusa-Maria & Maija, 2016; Grimes, 2019). Multi-grade teaching is a useful medium to promote social outcomes (Brown, 2010). The success of the implementation of multi-grade education greatly lies in the teacher who ascertains and believes that multi-grade teaching is worthwhile and the ultimate response to provide access to education for all (Kivunja and Sims, 2018).

Challenges of Multi-Grade Teaching

This category describes the multi-grade teachers' difficulties and challenging experiences in the delivery of multi-grade instruction that surfaced in the thematic analysis. Sixteen (16) out of the eighteen (18) studies mostly from developing and less developed countries of Asia and Africa mentioned that teachers expressed more issues and obstacles in their teaching jobs in multi-grade instruction.

Theme 4: Being left behind to teach on their own

Multi-grade schools are located in geographically isolated, disadvantaged, conflict-affected and sparsely populated communities. Hence, teachers are isolated, struggling on their own and seldom visited by subject specialists (Taole, 2014). This results to the feeling of professionally isolated of some rural teachers (Nitta et al, 2010). Isolation and loneliness affect their job fulfilment and ability to perform at their best (Sleppin, 2009). They also have fewer opportunity to exchange ideas, gain new skills, and interact with teacher educators and supervisors. (OECD, 2019). The isolation of teachers also makes it difficult to attract teachers to teach in remote rural areas (Juvane, 2007).

Theme 5: Inadequacy in Multi-grade teaching

Their feeling of incompetence stemmed from the lack of teacher preparations and in-service training, inadequate resources, lack of support from parents, colleagues and school heads for effective organization and planning (Gasa, 2016; Bua & Martin, 2020; Mulaudzi, 2016; Taole, 2014; Sampson & Condy, 2016; Taole & Mncube, 2012). The absence of such supports affects the quality of multi-grade instruction (SEAMEO INNOTECH, 2012). Their geographic isolation, small size, and socioeconomic mix, among other factors, are thought to enhance their chances of suffering from poor infrastructure, a lack of competent teachers, and limited educational offers (OECD, 2019).

They are untrained to teach and learn in rural settings because initial teacher preparation programs are mostly focused on approaches relevant to larger metropolitan schools (Ares Abalde, 2014; OECD, 2019; Kawuryan et al, 2021). The teachers felt that they needed good examples of implementing strategies in multi-grade teaching, in real and not ideal conditions. They opined that the greatest pedagogic challenges in the multigrade classroom were the differentiation and individualization of teaching (Brown, 2010); difficulty in completing the official curriculum and the need for flexible approach in teaching (OECD, 2019); and poor physical structure of buildings and deficiencies in equipment and resources (Cornish, 2010).

Theme 6: Difficulty in handling classroom and time management

Teachers had challenges in terms of applying differentiation, controlling noise in the classroom, and managing time in lesson preparations (Mulaudzi, 2016; Muusa-Maria & Maija, 2016; Erden, 2020; Ngubane, 2011; Rafiq & Sultana, 2020). Classroom Management situations, management of instructional time and supportive factors are among the various roadblocks that MG teachers faced in terms of efficiently implementing the multi-grade instruction (SEAMEO INNOTECH, 2019). According to Unal & Unal (2012), it is possibly the most difficult component of teaching for many teachers, and problems in this area force many people to stop teaching entirely.

Theme 7: Failing to address learners' diversity

Learners' different cognitive levels and learning styles, divergent behaviour and learning attitude were the most common challenges encountered by the teachers (Rafiq & Sultana, 2020). Teachers struggled in addressing academic diversity, ethnicity and culture in multi-grade schools (SEAMEO INNOTECH, 2019).

In terms of community, the learners mostly come from homes of farm workers—workers who have low levels of literacy and living in impoverished conditions (Cornish, 2010). This results in a lack of parental involvement, absenteeism, and high dropout rates (SEAMEO INNOTECH, 2019). Teachers at rural schools identified a need for specialized training in multicultural and multilingual education (OECD, 2019).

Nonetheless, rural instructors and leaders must learn how to interact with underrepresented or marginalized populations in rural areas, such as low-income families or indigenous and ethnic minority kids who may have less of an influence in the community (Jorgensen et al., 2010; Biddle et al, 2018). Schools in rural settings might be difficult to handle (OECD, 2019).

Theme 8: Experiencing burnout in teaching

They had overload of work in preparation, teaching and assessment. Overlapping of tasks as full-time teachers and carrying out administrative work were performed by the teachers (Taole & Mncube, 2012; Gasa, 2016; Mulaudzi, 2016). Such multiplicity of tasks had to compete for the attention and time of the multi-grade teacher (SEAMEO INNOTECH, 2019). They took on a variety of roles, including classroom teaching, sometimes across multiple grades, leading instruction and assessment in a variety of subject areas, managing tight school budgets, meeting increasing fundamental accountability and reporting requirements, and cultivating strong relationships with close-knit communities. (OECD, 2019).

Furthermore, they struggled to keep up school aims with the different interests of parents and the community, and they require a knowledge of the school's significant contribution to the community in particular, and society in general (Preston et al, 2013; OECD, 2019). The teaching and administrative workload required of a multi-grade teacher, result in overload and stress (Brown, 2010; Brunswic & Valérien, 2004; Little, 2006). Teachers' burnout, emotional fatigue, and detachment have a negative impact on their occupational well-being (Viac and Fraser, 2020).

Addressing the challenges in teaching

This category describes the multi-grade teachers' coping mechanism in responding the challenges they encountered in the delivery of multi-grade instruction that surfaced in the thematic analysis. Twelve out of the 18 studies from developing and less developed countries of Asia and Africa showed personal and professional qualities of teachers in addressing the challenges in multi-grade teaching.

Theme 9: Teachers' Resourcefulness

Teachers surpassed their challenges because of being resourceful. Teachers need to be resourceful given their circumstances. The lack of materials and support made teachers make their teaching materials (Taole, 2014). They often bring materials collected from home. They even bought materials from their own pocket (Ngubane, 2011). They collaborated with other stakeholders just to help their students with their basic needs like food. They also visited other MG schools and tried to look for best practices. These are some actions that showed teachers' resourcefulness. Teachers in isolated areas are often very resourceful (Cornish, 2010), making use of what is available and adapt to the situation (Quejada, & Orale, 2018).

Theme 10: Teachers' Innovativeness

Teaching Multi-grade developed teachers' innovativeness. They need to be innovative to cater to their unique situation. The lack of training on multi grade teaching made the teachers device their own methods, strategies, and management of the teaching and learning process. They devised their own strategies that fit their situations (Ramathan & Mzimela 2016); (Brown, 2010). Teachers need to innovate and develop abilities to keep up with the needed personal and organizational changes (Lecat et al. 2017; Arocena et al, 2007).

Theme 11: Teachers' Resiliency

Teachers survived and remained strong despite the challenges. Their experiences were their best teachers. They continue to learn and grow despite the hardship they encountered. They tried their best to deliver complex tasks (Taole, 2014) They tried to survive teaching multi grade by achieving objectives of learning. (Rafiq & Sultana, 2020). Through their pedagogical leadership traits, multi-grade teachers can provide models of teaching success through their resilience and adaptive skills (Ramathan and Ngubane, 2013)

Figure 1 below summarizes the experiences of teachers in multi-grade instruction across the globe. Teachers have varied experiences in multi-grade teaching and addresses the challenges they met by being resourceful, innovative and resilient.

Figure 2. Teachers' experiences in multi-grade instruction

Meta-Themes

Synthesizing the eleven (11) themes and its implications emerged two (2) meta-themes, namely: teacher preparation, and teacher training and mentoring which aimed on transforming teaching and learning in multi-grade instruction.

Teacher Preparation

Overall, a comprehensive system for teacher development including recruitment of qualified individuals into the teaching profession and their preparation are the most viable options to respond to all the challenges in multi-grade teaching (Darling-Hammond, 2013).

A strong pre-service teacher education program with supervision of qualified mentors and featuring a strong immersive internship through partnership with schools and community prepares well the multi-grade teacher (OECD, 2019). Trainings of teachers on multi-grade instruction to competently teach and execute their roles well as planners, organizers, managers, facilitators, observers, and assessors of learning that can be provided by the Higher Education Institutes.

Explicit topics which are relevant and with direct applications to the multi-grade context on differentiation, diversity and grouping of students, recognizing multiple intelligences, curriculum planning, use of appropriate materials and resources, effective time and classroom management, assessment and community relationships should be given utmost emphasis to ensure quality education to more ethnically and culturally diverse learning environments (OECD, 2019, Mulryan-Kyne, 2007).

Teacher preparation is the single most influential medium to shape teaching in multigrade classrooms and develop multi-grade teachers to be at the forefront in pedagogies, curriculum and technologies in multi-grade instruction (Brown, 2010).

Teacher Training and Mentoring

Multi-grade teaching is a continuous process. Induction, mentoring and certification programs on multi-grade instruction should respond to the needs of multi-grade teachers in the teaching learning process. Trainings provided by academic institutions that include orientation prior to deployment and mentoring greatly support in the actual multi-grade instruction (Brown, 2010).

The average teacher in a small rural school must constantly learn new things and develop his or her expertise in teaching in the challenging context of the multi-grade curriculum. They must acquire personal competencies that go beyond the standard initial and in-service teacher training curriculum, which are geared for traditional mono-grade teaching (Koulouris & Sotiriou, 2006).

Teachers need to be supported through in-service training workshops and collaborations among teachers and principals to ensure that they are guided in interpreting the curriculum, managing learning in special

circumstances, implementing teaching innovations in the classroom, improving personal competences and boosting their confidence as teachers in rural schools (Taole, 2014; Darling-Hammond, 2013; Joubert, 2010). Mentoring multi-grade teachers goes far beyond strategies. Hence, school system must work hard to sustain them, attain success and impact the lives of diverse students in isolated and marginalized communities.

Conclusion

Multi-grade teachers have multifaceted experiences and coping mechanism in teaching. Their personal and professional qualities made them stand despite of the challenges they encountered. Multi-grade teaching is a continuous training from teacher preparation to professional development. Academic institutions should provide pre-service and professional teachers comprehensive training for multi-grade teaching and diverse groups of students.

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